

Landscape Management and Wetland Protection in Agricultural Environments: Insights from the European Landscape Convention in the Baetic Countrysides

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Abstract

In European rural landscapes, particularly those intensively transformed by agricultural activities, the coexistence of high-value natural areas—mainly wetlands—represents a critical challenge for sustainable land planning. Following the principles of the European Landscape Convention (ELC), which promotes the protection, management, and planning of landscapes in all their forms, this study examines the role of planning and management strategies in the conservation and transformation of agricultural landscapes in wetland areas in the Guadalquivir Basin, Andalusia.

This research examines how public policies and landscape integration in land planning have shaped ecosystems, promoting sustainability, preserving

traditional agricultural landscapes, and naturalizing abandoned farmland. Using various sources and fieldwork, it highlights key changes, achievements, and challenges, stressing the need for holistic, community-driven approaches aligned with the ELC's guidelines.

This study offers an innovative perspective on the interaction between environmental conservation and agricultural dynamics, highlighting the importance of integrating wetlands into active landscape planning, not only to ensure their protection but also to optimize their ecological, social, and economic functionality within the European rural context. The study contributes to the operationalization of the European Landscape Convention, particularly through its emphasis on participatory governance (Articles 5 and 6) and the integration of landscape concerns into spatial planning.

Keywords: European Landscape Convention; Land planning; Landscape management; Wetlands; Baetic countrysides; Agricultural sustainability

I. Introduction

The research aligns with the principles of the European Landscape Convention (ELC) (Council of Europe, 2000), particularly its focus on integrating landscapes into territorial planning policies. The ELC emphasizes the sustainable management of landscapes, which is evident in the protection and management strategies applied to wetlands in the Baetic Countrysides. These efforts echo the Convention's objectives to promote the conservation of natural and cultural heritage and enhance public participation in landscape policies (Articles 1, 2, and 5). The study examines how these principles are applied in the Andalusian wetlands, highlighting both the challenges and opportunities for achieving sustainable landscape management.

Wetlands are habitats of great importance as they play a crucial role in environmental balance and quality. However, agricultural activity and land management can have a significant impact on these fragile environments (Borja, Camacho & Florín, 2012).

According to Cooper and Moore (2003), agriculture is a fundamental activity for human sustenance, but its expansion and inappropriate practices can negatively affect wetlands (Robles, 2007). Land drainage for cultivation, intensive use of fertilizers and pesticides, and excessive water extraction are some of the agricultural practices that can alter the hydrological processes and water quality of wetlands (Davis & Froend, 1999).

Territorial management also plays an important role in the relationship between wetlands and agricultural activity. Proper land use planning and the implementation of conservation measures are essential to mitigate the negative impacts of agriculture on wetlands. This involves establishing buffer zones around wetlands, promoting sustainable farming practices that minimize pollution, and encouraging the participation of local communities in the management and conservation of wetland areas.

It is important to recognize that the relationship between wetlands, agricultural activity, and territorial management is complex and multifaceted (Verhoeven & Setter, 2010). On one hand, wetlands can provide ecosystem services beneficial to agriculture, such as water flow regulation and the provision of habitats for pollinator species (Borja, Camacho & Florín, 2012). On the other hand, agriculture can have a negative impact on the biodiversity and services of wetlands if appropriate conservation and management measures are not adopted.

In the context of the human–environment dialectic, the impact of human activity on particularly valuable and fragile natural environments becomes especially relevant. Within this more specific framework, the present study aims to reflect on the issue in the case of agricultural activity and its development in inland wetland environments.

The case study will focus on the countryside areas of the Guadalquivir Basin (Andalusia, Spain). In this large and internally complex territory, we will select protected natural areas (wetlands) to examine the effects of protection on agricultural activity and on the ecological and landscape dynamics of the areas concerned.

These landscapes experience unprecedented anthropogenic pressure, which affects the scattered wetlands in various ways. Among the activities that occur in the vicinity of these lagoons—and that pose a serious risk to their proper functioning—are the emergence of rural constructions (from sizeable buildings to small country houses), competition for water resources, significant deforestation of areas surrounding the wetlands (through the burning of reed beds and the ploughing of wetland zones for cultivation), and the introduction of crops such as cereals, horticultural products, and olive groves into previously deforested areas. In the best-case scenario, only some riparian trees and patches of reed beds remain on the lagoon edges.

Because of these activities, there is often a loss of both plant and animal biodiversity, as well as the introduction of new species (Zedler, 2003). Cultivation near lagoons also causes soil erosion and sedimentation of the lagoon basins. Water quality is further affected using phytosanitary products,

hunting activities, and the construction of transport infrastructure in nearby areas, such as roads and/or railway lines.

This research seeks to evaluate the impact of human activity on the extent and quality of wetlands in highly anthropized areas. This objective aims to analyze how human activities such as urbanization, agriculture, or industry have modified the distribution and uses of wetlands in specific areas.

We also aim to identify the main drivers of land-use change that affect wetlands in anthropized zones. This objective seeks to understand land-use change patterns that have led to wetland loss or degradation, and to analyze the driving forces behind these changes, such as agricultural intensification.

Broadly speaking, our goal is to assess the effectiveness of territorial management in conserving critical spaces. To this end, we will analyze the implementation and outcomes of measures such as the establishment of protected areas, sustainable territorial and urban planning, and environmentally respectful farming practices in the conservation of wetlands.

Objectives outside the scope of this study—such as the analysis of habitat fragmentation effects on wetland conservation or the evaluation of the restoration potential of degraded wetlands through species reintroduction, watercourse rehabilitation, or reforestation of surrounding areas—will not be addressed here.

II. Geographical Context and Territorial Features

The Baetic countryside areas are located on the Iberian Peninsula, within the broad Guadalquivir Basin (Moreira, 2003). They span parts of four provinces in the Autonomous Community of Andalusia which, from west to east—following the course of the Guadalquivir River—are Jaén, Córdoba, Seville, and Granada.

This is a region of extraordinary fertility and extensive agricultural use, both historically and in the present day (Naranjo, 2013). It is characterized primarily by extensive, large-estate (*latifundia*) farming, although there are also signs of agricultural intensification and smallholding (*minifundia*) in specific areas.

The study area (Figure 1), located in southern Europe, covers approximately 1.5 million hectares, with a total perimeter of 6,751 km, oriented in a northeast–southwest direction (Table I).

It is situated in the southern half of the Guadalquivir Basin, just north of the initial foothills of the Baetic mountain ranges.

Fig. 1. Study area of the wetlands included in this research and the main localities near them.

Source: Naranjo, Torres & Vega (2016b)

Within this geographical area, there is a series of wetlands —most of which have a temporary hydrological regime— whose origin is determined by the factors that shape the hydrogeology of the Andalusian countryside. This hydrogeology is defined by the predominance of materials and lithologies belonging to the Guadalquivir Olistostrome Complex and the Subbetic Chaotic Complexes (Vera, 2004).

As a result, clay and marly low-permeability materials are predominant. From a hydrogeological perspective, these materials behave as an aquitard, containing brackish or saline water in most locations (Moya, 1988).

Table 1. Surfaces and perimeters of the different landscape areas considered in the study.

Landscape Zone	Area (ha)	Perimeter (km)
Foothill Countryside	147,939	1,279
Undulating, Rolling, and Hilltop Countryside	955,247	3,139
Valleys, Alluvial Plains, and Inland Marshes	416,675	2,333
TOTAL	1,519,861	6,751

Source: Own elaboration.

The existence of a large number of these wetlands, scattered across much of the countryside landscape (Figure 2), has been studied by authors such as Dantín (1940), Pardo (1948), Recio (1984), Montes & Martino (1987), González-Bernáldez (1987), Ortega, Parra & Guerrero (2003) and Vega (2018), whose research documents the intermittent presence of more than 220 wetlands.

Within this context, two main territorial realities are identified: isolated lagoons and endorheic complexes (lagoon clusters). To these, we must add several artificial water bodies that have undergone naturalization, such as the Cordobilla and Malpasillo reservoirs (located in the middle course of the Genil River, on the border between the provinces of Córdoba and Seville), along with others heavily shaped by anthropogenic influence, such as Laguna Grande (Jaén).

Fig. 2. Map with types of landscape that make up the Guadalquivir Basin.

Source: Own elaboration.

As noted in the introductory section, this research focuses on the most relevant wetlands—those that currently enjoy protected status and are therefore part of the Network of Protected Natural Areas of Andalusia (RENPA), with implications for spatial planning and management. These protected wetlands are located across the four provincial sectors that make up the Baetic countryside areas.

The first initiative in this regard was undertaken in the province of Córdoba in 1984, when a group of lagoons (Zóñar, Tíscar, Rincón, Amarga, Jarales, and Salobral) were declared Integral Reserves. Subsequently, in 1989, with the approval of a new Spanish law on the protection of natural areas¹ and the subsequent Andalusian environmental protection law, which established the regional inventory of protected natural areas—the precursor of the current RENPA (Network of Protected Natural Areas of Andalusia)²—, these Integral Reserves were reclassified as Natural Reserves—a designation

1 Law 4/1989, of March 27, on the Conservation of Natural Areas and Wild Flora and Fauna, later replaced by Law 42/2007, of December 13, on Natural Heritage and Biodiversity.

2 Law 2/1989, of July 18, approving the Inventory of Protected Natural Areas of Andalusia and establishing additional measures for their protection.

they still hold today. Moreover, the Andalusian Law on Protected Natural Areas also led to the declaration of the Cordobilla and Malpasillo reservoirs, as well as Laguna Grande, under the Natural Site category.

The proximity of these two sites to the wetlands explains their inclusion within the collective designation of the Wetlands of Southern Córdoba, which since 2011 has been subject to unified environmental planning through the approval of its Natural Resources Management Plan (PORN)³.

A similar model was adopted for the protection of the main wetlands located in the countryside areas of Cádiz—within the Guadalquivir River Basin. Indeed, some lagoons in this region were declared Integral Reserves in 1987 and were later reclassified as Natural Reserves under Regional Law 2/1989. However, it was not until more recently, in 2017, that a Natural Resources Management Plan (PORN) was approved for this group of wetlands⁴.

In the case of Seville, nearly all its wetlands were declared Natural Reserves under Law 2/1989. As in the case of Cádiz, however, a Natural Resources Management Plan (PORN) establishing a unified planning model for the Lagoons of Seville was not approved until 2017⁵.

Finally, in the Jaén sector, although its three protected wetlands were designated under Law 2/1989, a dual situation can be observed. On the one hand, Laguna del Chinche and Laguna Honda—which are located in proximity and were both declared Natural Reserves—share a single Natural

3 Decree 52/2011, of March 8, approving the Natural Resources Management Plan (PORN) for the Wetlands of Southern Córdoba.

4 Decree 1/2017, of January 10, declaring the following as Special Areas of Conservation (SACs): Complejo Endorreico de Espera (ES0000026), Laguna de Medina (ES0000027), and Complejo Endorreico de Chiclana (ES0000028), Complejo Endorreico del Puerto de Santa María (ES0000029), Complejo Endorreico de Puerto Real (ES0000030), Laguna de los Tollos (ES612001), Lagunas de Las Canteras y El Tejón (ES6120014), Laguna de La Ratosa (ES6170001), Lagunas de Campillos (ES6170015), Complejo Endorreico de Utrera (ES6180001), Decree 1/2017, of January 10, declaring the following areas as Special Areas of Conservation (ZEC): Complejo Endorreico de Espera (ES0000026), Laguna de Medina (ES0000027), Complejo Endorreico de Chiclana (ES0000028), Complejo Endorreico del Puerto de Santa María (ES0000029), Complejo Endorreico de Puerto Real (ES0000030), Laguna de los Tollos (ES612001), Lagunas de Las Canteras y El Tejón (ES6120014), Laguna de La Ratosa (ES6170001), Lagunas de Campillos (ES6170015), Complejo Endorreico de Utrera (ES6180001), Complejo Endorreico La Lantejuela (ES6180002), Laguna del Gosque (ES6180003), and Laguna de Coripe (ES6180006); and approving the Natural Resources Management Plan (PORN) for the Natural Reserves of the Wetlands of Cádiz, the Natural Resources Management Plan for the Natural Reserves of the Lagoons of Málaga, and the Natural Resources Management Plan for the Natural Reserves of the Lagoons of Seville.

5 Refer to the previous note.

Resources Management Plan (PORN), which was approved in 2015⁶; on the other hand, the Natural Site of Laguna Grande has had its own separate management plan since 2016⁷.

It is also necessary to mention the Andalusian Wetlands Plan (PAH), approved by the Resolution of November 4, 2002, which serves as both a legal and technical instrument providing legal protection for wetlands in Andalusia. This plan was developed by the Regional Ministry of the Environment (Consejería de Medio Ambiente) and involved the participation of scientists and technical experts in wetlands and endangered species management (Junta de Andalucía, 2002).

The PAH is considered a key tool for ensuring the conservation of Andalusia's wetland heritage, as well as for coordinating actions to be undertaken by the Regional Ministry of Environment and Spatial Planning with other governmental administrations². In addition, it contributes to the implementation and development in Andalusia of the Spanish Strategic Plan for the Conservation and Rational Use of Wetlands.

The plan sets out the principles and management criteria, sectoral programs, prioritized actions, and the necessary procedures to achieve a balance between maintaining ecological integrity and the sustainable use of resources. It also defines the environmental policy on wetlands for all the governing bodies within the Regional Ministry of the Environment (Junta de Andalucía, 2002).

III. METHODOLOGY

The study explores how the implementation of landscape protection policies in the Baetic Countrysides reflects the European Landscape Convention's guidelines (Council of Europe, 2000). The inclusion of protected wetlands within territorial planning emphasizes the need for sustainable development that harmonizes environmental, economic, and cultural interests (Articles 3 and 5). By examining the management of wetlands in Andalusia, this research demonstrates how landscape policies promote ecological

6 Decree 7/2015, of January 20, declaring the following sites as Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) within the European Natura 2000 Ecological Network: *Albufera de Adra* (ES610001) and *Laguna Honda* (ES616000); and approving the Natural Resources Management Plan (PORN) for the *Albufera de Adra Natural Reserve* and the *Natural Resources Management Plan for the Laguna Honda and Laguna del Chinche Natural Reserves*.

7 Decree 172/2016, of November 8, approving the Natural Resources Management Plan (PORN) for the Natural Sites *Alto Guadalquivir* and *Laguna Grande*.

integrity while fostering local community involvement in decision-making processes.

For the present study, a sequential analysis was conducted, structured in several phases: fieldwork, cartographic analysis, and planning review.

Once the research objectives were defined, the spatial distribution of wetlands, the changes in their extent due to human activity, and the identification of the main threats to their conservation were analyzed.

As a necessary step, a literature review was carried out by examining previous studies, maps, and geospatial data to understand the location, characteristics, and transformations of wetlands affected by human activities.

A key element was the selection of the study area. To that end, geographic zones hosting significant wetlands were identified. At this point, the use of satellite imagery, cartographic data, and geographic information systems (GIS) proved essential for identifying areas impacted by human activity, such as urban, industrial, or agricultural zones.

The methodology applied placed special emphasis on the collection of geospatial data, which enabled the acquisition of accurate information about the wetlands under study. This included satellite imagery, LiDAR data, aerial photographs, and historical maps. Remote sensing techniques were also used to obtain data on wetland extent, land use changes, and physical characteristics.

For geospatial analysis, GIS tools and spatial analysis methods were used to process the collected data. As will be shown below, wetland distribution maps were generated, land use change analyses were performed, spatial patterns of human impact were identified, and wetland fragmentation metrics were calculated.

To conduct a spatially explicit analysis of wetland transformation and pressures, we applied a combination of remote sensing and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) techniques.

Satellite imagery (Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8) was processed to detect changes in land use and wetland surface area over time (1985–2018), using supervised classification and post-classification comparison techniques. A normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) and normalized difference built-up index (NDBI) were used to assess vegetation cover and the extent of anthropogenic disturbance, respectively.

LiDAR data (provided by the Spanish National Geographic Institute) and historical orthophotographs were integrated to identify morphological alterations in lagoon basins and surrounding slopes. Watershed boundaries were delineated using digital elevation models (DEM) and hydrological tools in QGIS 3.28. Landscape metrics—such as edge density, patch cohesion, and

mean patch size—were calculated using FRAGSTATS software to assess habitat fragmentation and spatial heterogeneity.

These spatial analyses were complemented by field validation campaigns and participatory mapping with local stakeholders. The integrated geospatial approach allowed for a quantitative assessment of land use dynamics and spatial patterns of pressure, thus contributing to evidence-based landscape planning.

Our methodological framework was informed by the principles of the ELC, particularly in terms of stakeholder inclusion, landscape identity, and territorial governance.

In the interpretation of results, we relied on geospatial analyses, which allowed us to assess the trends and patterns identified. The interpretation of the findings, considering the information gathered during the literature review, will support conclusions based on geographical evidence.

This research was developed within the framework of Andalusian Wetlands Plan, supported by Regional Government of Andalusia. The methodology combines spatial analysis, participatory mapping, and planning review in alignment with international conventions such as the ELC.

IV. Results: Agriculture and Landscape Management in Protected Wetlands

Despite the significant progress made since the declaration of protected areas in the Baetic Countrysides, there are still challenges that hinder the full realization of the European Landscape Convention's objectives. These challenges include soil erosion, the over-exploitation of natural resources, and the agricultural pollution that continues to threaten wetland ecosystems. The findings underline the necessity for continuous improvements in the management plans, ensuring that they are adaptable and robust in addressing both environmental and societal needs -Articles 6 and 7- (Council of Europe, 2000).

The fact that the inland water bodies of the Andalusian Baetic countryside are geographically situated within a heavily agricultural landscape directly explains why the protected wetlands (Natural Reserves, along with the three Natural Sites considered in this study) include agricultural land within their boundaries (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Land uses within the limits of some of the wetlands under study: 1.- Laguna Amarga; 2.- Cordobilla Reservoir; 3. Lantejuela Endorheic Complex
 Source: Compiled by the author based on SIOSE (2018).

In this regard, the territorial model of the Natural Reserves (which constitute most of protected wetlands) is particularly noteworthy. Their planning framework establishes a dual zoning system: Core Reserve Zones (which essentially include the water basins and their immediate margins, subject to stricter conservation measures) and Peripheral Protection Zones (which encompass the surrounding wetland areas).

Table II. Protected wetlands in Andalusian Baetic countryside.

Wetland	Province	Protection status (year)	Other Protection Designations	Area (ha)	Peripheral Protection Zone (ha)
Laguna Grande	Jaén	Natural Site	ZEC, Ramsar Site	212	-
Laguna del Chinche	Jaén	Natural Reserve	Ramsar Site	5.4	124.5
Laguna Honda	Jaén	(1989)	ZEC, Ramsar Site	10.9	142.1
Laguna del Conde o Salobral	Córdoba	Natural Reserve	ZEC, ZEPA, Ramsar Site	73.4	260.7
Laguna de Zóñar	Córdoba	(1984)		75.7	321.5
Laguna de Tíscar	Córdoba			21.4	168.7
Laguna del Rincón	Córdoba			9.5	139.9
Laguna Amarga	Córdoba			12.2	276.8
Laguna de los Jarales	Córdoba			9	133.0
Embalse de Cordobilla	Córdoba-Sevilla	Natural Site (1989)	ZEPA, Ramsar Site	1460	-
Embalse de Malpasillo	Córdoba-Sevilla		ZEPA, Ramsar Site	512	-
Lantejuela Endorheic Complex	Sevilla	Natural Reserve (1989)	ZEC	67	829
Laguna del Gosque	Sevilla	Natural Reserve (1989)	ZEC, ZEPA	39.2	365.2
Utrera Endorheic Complex	Sevilla		ZEC	76.2	990.1
Lebrija-Las Ca-bezas Endorheic Complex	Sevilla		ZEC, ZEPA	54.3	814.2
Espera Endorheic Complex	Cádiz	Natural Reserve (1987)	ZEC, ZEPA, Ramsar Site	61.9	457.2

Source: Own elaboration.

The latter, which often cover much larger areas than the Core Reserve Zones (Table II), represent territories of significant environmental and territorial interest. Indeed, they host various human activities that exert a direct influence on the wetlands and their environmental dynamics. Therefore, ensuring compatibility between development and conservation through

appropriate spatial planning and territorial management is especially critical in these peripheral areas surrounding water bodies.

Fig. 4. Distribution (%) of the main land uses in protected wetlands of the Baetic Countryside (2018). Based on the Natural Resources Management Plans (PORN) (2018). Source: Own elaboration based on the Natural Resources Management Plans (PORN) of the Natural Reserves and Natural Sites of the Wetlands of Southern Córdoba and the Lagoons of Seville.

* In the case of the Natural Reserves, both the Core Reserve Zone and the Peripheral Protection Zone are considered.

The geospatial analysis revealed distinct land use transformation patterns across the wetlands studied. Between 1985 and 2018, more than 60% of the Peripheral Protection Zones experienced shifts in dominant land use types, with a marked increase in intensive cropping and a corresponding decline in shrubland and natural vegetation.

NDVI time-series analyses demonstrated a significant reduction in vegetation density during the spring and summer months in the watersheds of Laguna del Rincón and Laguna Honda, indicative of increased land degradation and erosion risk. In contrast, areas with reforestation programs—such as Zóñar—showed moderate vegetation recovery, as supported by field observations.

The spatial distribution of anthropogenic pressures was notably clustered around southeastern slopes with high soil exposure, particularly in the Jaén and Córdoba sectors. Edge density and patch fragmentation metrics

confirmed that natural habitat continuity has been increasingly disrupted in buffer zones less than 500 meters from lagoon margins.

These results underscore the relevance of applying remote sensing and GIS tools to identify critical zones of intervention, prioritize conservation efforts, and monitor compliance with land use regulations outlined in the Natural Resources Management Plans (PORNs).

A more detailed look at the geographical reality of the wetlands analyzed—through the examination of major land uses, based on information provided by the respective Natural Resources Management Plans (PORN) (Figure 4)—reveals that, in contrast to the minor or merely symbolic presence of land uses such as forest formations or artificial surfaces (buildings or infrastructure), agricultural land occupies the dominant share.

Among these agricultural uses, croplands are clearly predominant (with pastures playing a much more limited role), demonstrating that the protection of these areas—implemented since the 1980s, as previously mentioned—has not substantially altered the agricultural character of the surroundings of these water bodies. In fact, the diverse composition of cropland types among the different wetlands (Figure 3) reflects the distinct characteristics of the countryside areas across provincial sectors. A clear contrast is evident between the dominance of woody crops (mainly olive groves) in the wetlands of Jaén and Córdoba (located in high countryside areas), and the predominance of herbaceous crops in Seville and Cádiz (located in lowland countryside zones, apart from *Laguna del Gosque*).

Based on this general observation, we proceed to a more specific analysis of agricultural activity in the selected sites, considering the key aspects of land-use planning and its impact on the evolution of farming practices as well as on the conservation of protected wetland ecosystems and landscapes.

In this regard, the primary reference for this more detailed approach is the protection regime established in environmental planning documents, namely the PORN. The essential contribution of these planning instruments—due to their nature as physical and regulatory tools—lies in the definition of a legal framework that, in practice, is largely similar across all the protected areas studied, with only minor adaptations in certain cases (Table III).

As can be observed, in the case of Natural Reserves, a clearly differentiated regulatory framework is applied to Core Reserve Zones and Peripheral Protection Zones, whereas in Natural Sites, the regulation is very similar to that of the latter.

Table III. Main aspects of the normative regulation of agricultural uses in protected wetlands.

Core Reserve Zones	<p>As a general rule, any use or activity likely to alter the natural characteristics of the lagoons is prohibited, particularly those that may affect the quantity and quality of their waters and their surrounding vegetation belt, except when such actions are directly related to management and aimed at the conservation of the area. Specifically, the following activities are prohibited:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Agricultural, forestry, and livestock uses (except those carried out within the peripheral lagoon belt, when deemed compatible with its protective function) (2) The construction or installation of buildings, infrastructure, or facilities of any kind (except those related to birdwatching activities).
Peripheral Protection Zones	<p>Forestry Activities and Uses:</p> <p>Afforestation of agricultural land is subject to a prior notification regime when it is carried out using native species, does not involve the removal of pre-existing forest vegetation, and the average slope of the intervention area does not exceed 15%;</p> <p>The following activities are subject to prior authorization:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) The afforestation of agricultural land, which must in all cases be carried out using native species, when it involves the removal of existing forest vegetation or when the average slope of the intervention area exceeds 15%; (2) Phytosanitary treatments on forest land, which under no circumstances may be carried out by aerial means. <p>The following are prohibited:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) The change of land use in forest areas; (2) Clearing with soil removal on slopes greater than 20%. <p>Agricultural Uses</p> <p>Subject to prior notification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The removal of woody crops located outside the contributing watershed of the lagoons. When the average slope of the intervention area exceeds 15%, the crop must be replaced—within a period not exceeding one year—by another tree or woody crop that provides soil cover equal to or greater than the previous one. <p>Subject to prior authorization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The consolidation and improvement of existing irrigation systems. – The removal of woody crops located within the contributing watershed of the lagoons. When the average slope of the intervention area exceeds 15%, the crop must be replaced—within a period not exceeding one year—by another tree or woody crop that ensures equal or greater soil coverage. Until the new plantation provides sufficient ground cover, measures must be taken to prevent soil erosion. – The removal of live hedges along boundaries, roads, and between plots.

	<p>Prohibited activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cropping within lagoons located in Peripheral Protection Zones. – The establishment of plastic-covered crops. – New irrigation systems (in the PORN for the Natural Reserves of Cádiz, those located within the contributing watershed of the lagoons may be authorized under very specific conditions). – Tillage against contour lines. – Terracing for soil preparation. – Aerial application of phytosanitary products on agricultural land. – The use of fire in agricultural tasks, except when strictly necessary for phytosanitary reasons. – In areas with severe erosion problems, tillage may be restricted, and the application of no-till or conservation tillage techniques may be required. <p>Livestock Uses</p> <p>Prohibited activities:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Confined livestock farming operations; 2) Burning of vegetation to obtain new pasture; 3) Grazing within the lagoon basins and their surrounding riparian formations.
Natural Sites	<p>Forestry Activities and Uses:</p> <p>The regulations are practically identical to those applicable in the Peripheral Protection Zones of the Natural Reserves.</p> <p>Agricultural Uses:</p> <p>The regulations are very similar to those established for the Peripheral Protection Zones of the Natural Reserves. The main differences lie in:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) The application of a prior notification regime (not requiring authorization) for the removal of woody crops, even when the average slope of the intervention area exceeds 15% (in which case, the crop must still be replaced within one year and erosion prevention measures must be adopted); (2) The possibility of authorizing new irrigation systems. <p>Livestock Uses:</p> <p>The regulations are identical to those applicable in the Peripheral Protection Zones of the Natural Reserves.</p>

Source: Own elaboration based on the Natural Resources Management Plans (PORN) of the Natural Reserves and Natural Sites of the Wetlands of Southern Córdoba and the Lagoons of Seville.

In the case of Core Reserve Zones, the PORNs reaffirm the legal mandate that establishes a total prohibition and abandonment of agricultural uses—except in cases of specifically justified compatibility within the peripheral lagoon vegetation belt. Although this issue lies beyond the scope of the present study, it could lead to environmental and landscape effects, such as the abandonment of certain cultivated areas and the recovery of natural vegetation.

By contrast, in Peripheral Protection Zones and Natural Sites, agricultural exploitation is generally permitted, though under specific conditions. These areas are governed by a set of authorized and prohibited activities designed to ensure compatibility with the conservation of habitats and species of Community interest associated with lagoon ecosystems. As such, the regulation of these peripheral environments emphasizes certain agricultural practices that enable such compatibility.

The public administration is aware of the need to prevent erosion processes that lead to sedimentation in the lagoons. This is addressed by ensuring vegetative soil cover—particularly during crop change or uprooting—and by prohibiting highly impactful practices such as land terracing for cultivation or tilling against contour lines on sloped terrain.

In addition, the regulations are sensitive to practices that may impact climatic conditions, such as aerial pesticide application, the use of fire, land-use changes from forestry to agriculture, or farming and grazing activities within the basins of seasonal lagoons located in these Peripheral Zones.

Lastly, the prevention of landscape impacts is also emphasized (Verhoeven, 2014), which explains the prohibition of certain practices such as plastic-covered crops or terracing, among other restrictions.

The planning instruments governing the studied wetlands include, among their strategic lines of action, the following measures related to these issues:

- Promotion of initiatives aimed at minimizing erosion risks in the contributing watersheds of the lagoons, particularly through reforestation with soil-protective purposes and the installation of sediment-retention structures (Figure 5).
- The possibility of acquiring or exchanging land within contributing basins to ensure conservation and sustainable management of natural resources. Protecting watersheds is essential for maintaining ecosystem integrity and ensuring water quality and quantity. This can be achieved through sustainable land-use planning, regulation of human activity in adjacent areas, and restoration of degraded wetlands.
- The establishment of restrictions on tillage, and the promotion of no-till or conservation tillage techniques in areas with severe erosion issues. Various measures can be applied to combat erosion in these zones, such as the planting of Mediterranean vegetation to stabilize soils and reduce runoff, the construction of terraces and embankments on slopes,

the use of vegetative cover crops, the creation of grasslands, and the implementation of controlled drainage systems to regulate water flow in tributary streams.

Hydrological correction works carried out in many streams and small rivers help reduce flood velocity, but these are merely containment measures applied to the final, already channelized sections, and do not address the root of the problem, which lies in the cultivated areas of the upper basins.

Moreover, agri-environmental measures under the Rural Development Plans (RDPs) and eco-schemes of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) promote the adoption of environmentally friendly cultivation practices by farmers. It is hoped that in the short to medium term, these measures will minimize the harmful effects of human activity on the natural environment, especially in endorheic lagoons, where all sediment from watershed erosion accumulates at the bottom of the lagoon.

Fig. 5. Hydrological corrections in the watershed of the Laguna de Zóñar Natural Reserve (TM Aguilar de la Frontera).

Source: Regional Ministry of Sustainability and Environment; Government of Andalusia (2018)

Fig. 6. Repopulation with riparian vegetation on the shore of the Zóñar lake (TM Aguilar de la Frontera).

Source: Regional Ministry of Sustainability and Environment; Government of Andalusia (2023)

An example of this is the restoration of lagoon basins previously affected by drainage and desiccation processes for agricultural use. Such is the case of Laguna de Santiago and Laguna Dulce, both located in the province of Córdoba.

In this regard, actions are also envisaged to gradually eliminate unnecessary and abandoned artificial structures. Where removal is not feasible, measures are proposed to integrate these elements into the landscape.

Finally, it is established that all interventions involving the construction or rehabilitation of infrastructure, facilities, and buildings must prioritize landscape integration and minimize visual impact. One illustrative case is the shoreline revegetation carried out at Zóñar Lake, which is shown in Figure 6.

V. Discussion

The natural and landscape value of Baetic countryside wetlands distinguishes this intensively cultivated region, shaped by strong human intervention.

The singularity, rarity, and diversity of habitats hosted by these wetlands allow for the survival of plant and animal species of great interest, their high biological diversity, and the uniqueness of the physical-biological processes that created and sustained them.

The watersheds of the Baetic countryside wetlands are mainly located in agricultural areas, dedicated to both rainfed and irrigated herbaceous crops, as well as olive groves and vineyards.

Wetlands in agricultural landscapes can play a vital role in biodiversity conservation and provide a range of ecosystem services, such as water quality control and climate change mitigation (Čížková et al., 2011). However, they are also vulnerable to pollution and degradation due to agricultural expansion and unregulated urban growth (Robles, 2007; Rojas et al., 2019). It is essential to integrate wetland management into agricultural systems to ensure that these ecosystems continue to fulfill their functional roles.

In line with this, it can be stated that, despite nearly 40 years since their designation, these wetlands face serious conservation challenges. Two major threats stand out: erosion and the resulting sedimentation, and agricultural pollution.

The key to understanding the high ecological value of the Baetic countryside wetlands lies in the presence of these isolated water bodies in a landscape that has been historically and intensely transformed by agricultural practices. These wetlands have intrinsic ecological importance, but also serve as refuge, feeding, resting, and breeding areas for numerous migratory bird species, due to their strategic location along migratory routes.

Their integration into spatial planning instruments has been a critical step in the real protection of their values, but it remains only an initial stage that requires further improvement. Their management plans need a renewed planning impetus. In this regard, it is necessary to ensure that all activities within their contributing watersheds—including agricultural operations involving earth movement—do not generate impacts that affect the wetlands, or compromise soil stability and erosion susceptibility.

Additionally, a revision of the protection boundaries is needed, adapting them to current knowledge about these systems, including their watersheds, aquifers, and hydrogeological functioning.

At the same time, the measures included in the Rural Development Plans (RDPs) and the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) do not appear sufficient to generate a meaningful shift toward a different model of agricultural use in the lagoon surroundings.

Intelligent solutions must be sought, aimed at promoting agricultural systems that are both compatible with wetland conservation and economically

viable and competitive for farmers. Agri-environmental measures tailored to these needs could help transform farmers into allies of environmental protection. Working along these lines is essential for achieving success. However, it would be desirable for such measures to be applied not only to the current 500-meter buffer zones—in the best of cases—but to the entire contributing watershed of each lagoon.

Considering all the above, it is imperative to implement corrective measures in collaboration with the various public administrations involved. Given the current social, economic, and agricultural conditions in these regions, such measures should be applied to the entire watershed of each wetland, not merely to their designated Peripheral Protection Zones.

To achieve a sustainable balance between agricultural activity and wetland conservation, an integrated approach is essential—one that considers ecological, social, and economic dimensions. This includes promoting sustainable farming practices that reduce agrochemical use, encourage soil conservation, and balance agricultural production with wetland protection. Moreover, it is necessary to strengthen governance and stakeholder participation, including farmers and local communities, in decision-making processes related to land management and wetland conservation.

VI. Conclusions

In conclusion, the relationship between wetlands, agricultural activity, and territorial management is complex and multifaceted, requiring a holistic and balanced approach. The adoption of sustainable agricultural practices, adequate land-use planning, and the engagement of local communities are essential to ensure the conservation of wetlands and the ecosystem services they provide. Maintaining a balance between agricultural productivity and wetland preservation is crucial to guarantee the long-term sustainability of both.

This research introduces innovative methodologies, such as the use of geospatial technologies and remote sensing to monitor the changes in wetland ecosystems. These techniques provide valuable insights into the interplay between agricultural practices and landscape conservation, which aligns with the ELC's call for innovative approaches in the management of European landscapes—Articles 5 and 6—(Council of Europe, 2000). This novel application of technology offers a more comprehensive understanding of how to balance landscape protection with agricultural development.

Furthermore, the findings of this study offer valuable contributions to the practical implementation and continued evolution of the European Landscape Convention. They underscore the potential of spatial planning and environmental governance tools to promote participatory approaches, as outlined in Articles 5 and 6 of the ELC. The integration of agricultural stakeholders and local communities into landscape decision-making processes —especially in the management of Peripheral Protection Zones— could enhance the effectiveness and legitimacy of conservation strategies. In this sense, the territorial insights drawn from the Baetic countryside wetlands provide a basis for developing participatory governance models that reconcile landscape protection with rural development priorities.

This case study demonstrates how ELC-aligned practices —such as inclusive landscape planning and integration of local actors— can support adaptive and participatory conservation strategies.

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Legal Documents

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